

Unraveling viscosity effects on the hysteresis losses of magnetic nanocubes

Received 00th January 20xx,
Accepted 00th January 20xx

DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

www.rsc.org/

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Hysteresis losses in magnetic nanoparticles constitute the basis of magnetic hyperthermia for delivering a local thermal stress. Nevertheless, this therapeutic modality is only to be realised through a careful appraisal of the best possible intrinsic and extrinsic conditions to the nanoparticles for which they maximise and preserve their heating capabilities. Low frequency (100 kHz) hysteresis loops accurately probe the dynamical magnetic response of magnetic nanoparticles in a more reliable manner than calorimetry measurements, providing conclusive quantitative data under different experimental conditions. We consider here a set of iron oxide or cobalt ferrite nanocubes of different sizes, through which we experimentally and theoretically study the influence of the viscosity of the medium on the low frequency hysteresis loops of magnetic colloids, and hence their ability to produce and dissipate heat to the surroundings. We analyse the role of nanoparticle size, size distribution, chemical composition, and field intensity in rendering the magnetisation dynamics sensitive to viscosity. Numerical simulations using the stochastic Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert equation model the experimental observations in excellent agreement. These results represent an important contribution towards predicting viscosity effects and hence to maximise heat dissipation from magnetic nanoparticles regardless of the environment.

Introduction

Heat dissipation due to hysteresis losses in magnetic materials generally constitutes a difficult issue to circumvent. But in the case of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs), heat losses are exploited for treating tumors in the so called magnetic hyperthermia therapy.¹ Under alternating magnetic fields (AMF), MNPs release heat to their surroundings leading to a local temperature elevation -typically up to 43°C- that destroy malignant tissues.²⁻³ A handful of clinical trials have employed MNPs as magnetic heating mediators with partial success depending on the cancer type²⁻³. Learnt lessons evidence that the current understanding of the physical parameters controlling magnetic heating at the nanoscale still needs to be improved, thus precluding the development of suitable instrumentation and clinical protocols. In this regard, viscosity (η) is one of the less studied physical parameters that affect nanoparticle heating efficiency.⁴⁻⁵ Fortin et al. presented one of the few comprehensive experimental studies considering the influence of the medium viscosity, and found a strong

decrease of heat dissipation while increasing the viscosity of the medium.⁶ This effect, as expected, is far more pronounced in highly anisotropic systems, like cobalt ferrites. The underlying reason is related to the magnetic relaxation processes (i.e. Néel or Brownian mechanisms) causing heat dissipation.⁶⁻⁷ Whereas Néel relaxation is related to the reorientation of the particle magnetic moment, Brownian relaxation is related to the particle rotation for reorienting its magnetic moment. These relaxation processes are ruled by different parameters such as MNP size,⁷ or magnetic anisotropy constant,⁶ that significantly determine the relaxation mechanisms responsible of magnetic heating. In addition, magnetic dipolar interactions⁸ or magnetic field intensity⁹⁻¹¹ have shown to significantly influence the relaxation mechanisms responsible of heat losses. In absence of magnetic field, the relaxation times are given by the following expressions⁹ for Néel and Brownian processes, respectively:

$$\tau_N = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{KV/k_B T}} \tau_0 e^{-KV/k_B T} \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_B = \frac{3\eta V_H}{k_B T} \quad (2)$$

where τ_0 is the inverse attempt frequency, K is the magnetic anisotropy constant, V is the nanoparticle volume, k_B is the Boltzman constant, T is the nanoparticle temperature, V_H is the hydrodynamic volume. Although the faster mechanism dominates, both mechanisms coexist, are coupled through a torque,¹⁰ and contribute to a different extent to the magnetic heat dissipation. While the Brownian relaxation renders heat dissipation of MNPs sensitive to η , Néel relaxation is not influenced by η at all.

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Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: [details of any supplementary information available should be included here]. See DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Figure 1 : Viscosity dependence of AC hysteresis loops under AMF (100 kHz and 24 kA/m) for A) 14 nm IONCs, B) 24 nm IONCs, C) 21 nm CoFeNCs at $1g_{Fe}/L$. Solid lines are experimental values, dashed lines are numerical simulations described in Material and Methods.

Considering the interaction of MNP and biological entities, recent studies^{12–15} have shown that the magnetic heating efficiency is significantly reduced when MNPs are located inside cells or tissues. The soundest explanation of such behaviour is related to either the increase of viscosity^{16–17} and/or nanoparticle aggregation^{18–20} imposed by the host biological matrices. Whereas aggregation effects have been explored and understood in terms of magnetic dipolar effects,^{21–22} little is known about the parameters ruling viscosity effects. Hence, it is crucial to unveil what determines those viscosity effects to predict any derived underperformance and choose the right MNP design strategy in order to avoid variations of magnetic heat losses related to their surroundings. Successive computational models describing hysteresis losses —with emphasis on their application to magnetic hyperthermia— have been developed in parallel to the experimental research on viscosity effects during last years.¹ Many of them derive from the seminal Rosensweig's model,⁷ which constituted a first attempt to calculate the heating losses of MNPs. Mamiya et al considered different scenarios upon the ratio between the externally applied AMF and the anisotropy field (H_K) of the MNPs¹⁰ and performed numerical simulations based on the coupling of the mechanical and magnetic torques behind the Brownian and Néel relaxation mechanisms. Using a kinetic Monte-Carlo method, several works proposed a unified model for heating

Figure 2 : Viscosity dependence of SAR values for 14 nm (black dots) and 24 nm (red dots) IONCs and 21 nm CoFeNCs (blue dots) under AMF (100 kHz and 24 kA/m) at $1g_{Fe}/L$. Lines are a guide to the eye.

mediated by MNPs to improve Rosensweig's theory that included interparticle interactions,^{23–25} a topic of increasing interest in nanoparticle-mediated magnetic hyperthermia. One of the most remarkable aspects of this model is that it offers a common “umbrella” to the underlying nanoparticle heating mechanisms across the transition from the superparamagnetic regime to the metastable hysteresis one. So far, Usov and Liubimov presented —perhaps the only one— a model with a rigorous treatment of viscosity effects on nanoparticle heating.²⁶ They first coined the terms *viscous* and *magnetic modes*, established according to the ratio between field intensity (H_{MAX}) and H_K .

Besides, calorimetry measurements are currently employed to quantify the MNP heat dissipation under changing conditions of concentration, or aggregation,^{10, 21, 23, 25, 27–28} in spite of the potential error sources in measuring and determining SAR values, which are difficult to keep under control.^{29–30} However, hysteresis loop measurements under AMF are the most direct and accurate tool to probe heat losses as a function of different extrinsic or intrinsic parameters such as particle aggregation,²¹ or concentration,^{21, 31} especially for the sake of comparison with theoretical models.²¹ For instance, how medium viscosity influences the AC hysteresis loops of MNPs is still an open question, which requires to be properly addressed.

The present study merges the choice of bespoke nanoparticle systems, consisting in a set of cobalt ferrite and iron oxide nanocubes with increasing magnetic anisotropy, with a suitable theoretical model for hysteresis losses featuring distinct considerations to best explain the actual role of viscosity on the dynamical magnetic response of MNPs. The role of nanoparticle size, size distribution, chemical composition, and field intensity in rendering the dynamical magnetic response sensitive to viscosity is studied.

Results and discussion

In order to probe the role of the above mentioned intrinsic and extrinsic parameters on the viscosity effects, iron oxide

Figure 3 : Viscosity dependence of M_R , M_{MAX} , H_C and A extracted from Fig.2 for 21 nm CoFeNCs (blue dots) , 24 nm (red dots) and 14nm (black dots) IONCs under AMF (100 kHz and 24 kA/m). Lines are a guide to the eye.

nanocubes (IONCs) of edge size (l_c) 14 ± 2 nm and 24 ± 4 nm, and cobalt ferrite nanocubes (CoFeNCs) of 21 ± 2 nm were studied (see ESI for more details related to MNP synthesis and characterisation). This set of MNPs allows one to probe the viscosity effects while progressively increasing KV by changing either size (i.e. V ranging from 1.4×10^{-24} to 2.7×10^{-23} m³) or MNP chemical composition³² (cobalt ferrite $K=290$ kJ/m³, magnetite $K=-13$ kJ/m³). This is thanks to the recently developed chemical routes³³⁻³⁴ that supply iron oxide and cobalt ferrite nanocubes with precise control of size and morphology, then resulting in outstanding SAR values. According to the Stoner-Wohlfarth model³⁵, heat losses in magnetic materials are proportional to K . The magnetisation cycles of the studied MNPs at 260 K show different hysteretic behaviour (Figure S2), more pronounced for CoFeNCs, negligible for 14 nm IONCs, and intermediate for 24 nm IONCs. Such different magnetic properties of MNPs under quasi-static conditions agree with the expected trend of the KV values for the studied MNPs. Furthermore, similar tendency will be also observed in the dynamical magnetisation response, including magnetic heating efficiency that clearly varies with chemical composition (i.e. K) and size (i.e. V).⁶ Additionally, MNPs shape³⁶, surface defects,³⁷ coating³⁸ or core/shell nanostructure³⁹ also influence the K value, and therefore, modulate the magnetic heating efficiency. The studied magnetic colloids present a homogenous cubic shape, and do not aggregate in the studied viscous media (see Figure S1 in ESI).

SAR values are commonly determined to appraise viscosity effects on the dynamical magnetic response of MNPs. Considering that $SAR = A \cdot f$, one may expect that any variation of SAR values with η will be translated into variations of shape and area of the corresponding AC hysteresis loops. In order to verify this point, we have measured hysteresis loops at different viscosity values ranging from 0.9 to 153.5 m-Pas and under AMF conditions (100 kHz and $H_{MAX}=24$ kA/m), which are very close to the ones currently employed in magnetic hyperthermia treatments.² Figures 1A-C shows the representative viscosity dependence of the hysteresis loops for the studied MNPs. As expected, the opening of the AC hysteresis loops under the same conditions significantly depends on MNPs, and hence the KV value.

Figure 4 : Frequency dependence of χ'_{AC} (thick lines) and χ''_{AC} (thin lines) for 21 nm CoFeNCs (upper figure) and 14nm IONCs (lower figure) dispersed in different viscous media. Dotted lines correspond to numerical simulation of χ''_{AC} described in ESI. Dashed lines indicate the AMF frequency experimentally employed in SAR and AC magnetization measurements.

Indeed, the AC hysteresis loops are less opened in case of IONCs (independently of size) than in case of CoFeNCs. The latter are also highly sensitive to η in comparison to IONCs, whose viscosity effects diminishes with particle size. Such viscosity behaviour is similar to the trend observed for the SAR under similar experimental conditions (see Figure 2). Indeed, SAR values of CoFeNCs are twice larger than those of IONCs (CoFeNCs : 440 W/g; 24 nm IONCs : 205 W/g; 14 nm IONCs : 120 W/g for $\eta = 0.9$ mPa·s) as expected due to the different KV values. By increasing η , the SAR values of CoFeNCs show an exponential decrease down to 4 W/g. Contrarily, the SAR behaviour depends on IONC size. While large IONCs display a progressive reduction of SAR values down to 38 W/g when increasing η , the small ones show slight reduction down to 98 W/g. This viscosity dependence of SAR is not related to MNP agglomeration^{21, 40} since MNP hydrodynamic size does not change upon dispersion in glycerol up to 32% vol. (see Figures S1 G-I). Further analysis of the AC hysteresis loops evidence the related viscosity effects. On the one hand, AC hysteresis loops of CoFeNCs feature a reduction of all characteristic hysteresis parameters (i.e. coercive field (H_C), remanence (M_R), and maximum magnetisation (M_{MAX})) when increasing viscosity as shown in Figure 3. On the other hand, the viscosity changes of shape and the area of AC hysteresis loops for IONCs depend on particle size. Whereas M_R and M_{MAX} decrease for both IONC sizes, but in a more pronounced manner for the larger size, H_C does not vary with viscosity for any size (see Figure 3D). Hence, the shape and area of the AC hysteresis loops for the larger IONCs behave differently with η , similarly to those of CoFeNCs. Furthermore, the variation of A with η (Figure 3B) matches the

Figure 5: Viscosity dependences of the field-dependent relaxation times and AC normalized M - H curves calculated as described in Materials and Methods for IONCs under AMF (100kHz) and different values of l_c and H_{MAX} . A, B) $l_c = 14$ nm and $H_{MAX} = 4$ kA/m, C, D) $l_c = 20$ nm and $H_{MAX} = 4$ kA/m, E, F) $l_c = 14$ nm and $H_{MAX} = 24$ kA/m, and G, H) $l_c = 20$ nm and $H_{MAX} = 24$ kA/m.

respective SAR dependence (Figures 1 and 2). As revealed in Figures 3A and C, the viscosity dependence of A is intimately associated with demagnetising effects, i.e. reduction of M_R and M_{MAX} , depending on the considered MNP. However, the role of H_C on determining the viscosity dependence of A values is not straightforward due to the complex interplay between different parameters involved in the MNPs magnetisation dynamics (mainly, K , H_{MAX} , and size distribution). Whereas H_C shows a progressive decrease with η for CoFeNCs, it remains constant for IONCs. According to the correlation of the viscosity dependences of SAR and A , the variation of AC hysteresis loops with η seems to be related to changes in the magnetic relaxation mechanisms as originally proposed by Fortin et al.⁶ In order to confirm this hypothesis, we have analysed the magnetic relaxation processes by AC susceptibility (ACS) measurements on the most and least sensitive MNPs to η . At a first glance, Figure 4 shows that the Brownian mechanism dominates the relaxation processes for those MNPs whose dynamical magnetic response is sensitive to viscosity (i.e. CoFeNCs) under the applied AMF conditions (i.e. 100 kHz, see dotted line in Figure 4). The contrary applies for the Néel mechanism (i.e. 14nm IONCs). For CoFeNCs, the real (χ'_{AC}) and imaginary (χ''_{AC}) parts of AC susceptibility clearly reflect the sole contribution of the Brownian relaxation. χ'_{AC} decays down to zero at high frequencies and χ''_{AC} exhibits a pronounced maximum that shifts towards lower frequencies when increasing η . It is worth noting that from the variation of χ''_{AC} values at a frequency of 100 kHz for different viscosities, we can qualitatively describe the viscosity dependences of A (i.e. SAR) in spite of the strong differences of the field intensity values ($H_{MAX} = 24$ kA/m and 0.07 kA/m for AC hysteresis loop and ACS measurements, respectively). χ''_{AC} at 100 kHz reaches zero when increasing η for CoFeNCs, similarly to the viscosity dependences observed for A and SAR values. In contrast, both

Brownian and Néel relaxation processes coexist in the 14nm IONCs. Whereas the Brownian peak shifts towards lower frequencies when increasing η , a less pronounced maximum is observed around 60 kHz within the frequency range associated with Néel relaxation. However, for the 14 nm IONCs χ''_{AC} does not reach zero at high frequencies even for the highest η because a broad Néel relaxation maximum peaked around 60 kHz is observed for $\eta = 97.3$ mPa.s. The complex Debye model (see ESI) can describe the AC susceptibility response of the studied MNPs in good agreement with the experimental results. The values of fitting parameters were comparable to experimental ones (Tables S3 and S4). It is worth noting that AC susceptibility measurements were performed at rather low field amplitudes (i.e. 0.07 kA/m) so that the zero-field expressions hold for τ_B and τ_N . In spite of the recently reported influence of H_{MAX} on magnetic dynamics¹¹, Néel relaxation prevails for 14 nm IONCs at the AMF conditions employed in SAR and AC hysteresis loop measurements (i.e. 100 kHz and 24 kA/m).

In order to precisely understand our experimental observation, numerical simulations based on the stochastic Landau–Lifshitz–Gilbert (LLG) equations were performed. From a theoretical point of view, the viscosity dependencies of AC hysteresis loops can be directly related to the prevalence of different relaxation mechanisms as extracted from Figure 4. Thus, for high KV values (i.e., CoFeNCs and 24 nm IONCs), AC hysteresis loops are highly sensitive to η due to the prevalence of Brownian relaxation when field intensity is taken into account (see ESI). On the contrary, low KV values (i.e., 14 nm IONCs) lead to a decrease of the viscosity influence when the Néel relaxation times (τ_{Neff}) are shorter than τ_{Beff} (Figure 5E,G). Hence, AC hysteresis loops of CoFeNCs are highly sensitive to viscosity (Figure S6B) because τ_{Beff} is much smaller than τ_{Neff} (Figure S6A). Unlikely, 14 nm IONCs present no viscosity effects on the dynamical magnetic response when τ_{Neff} are shorter

Figure 6: Viscosity dependence of AC hysteresis loops under AMF (100 kHz and 4 kA/m) for 14 nm IONCs at $1g_{\text{Fe}}/L$. Solid lines are experimental values, dashed lines are numerical simulations described in Materials and Methods. For the sake of clarity, magnetization values are increased 3-fold.

than τ_{Beff} (Figure 6E-H). The consideration of these different magnetic dynamics in the LLG equations (see ESI) provides a suitable theoretical framework to simulate AC hysteresis loops (dotted lines in Figure 1), resulting in good agreement with the experimental results (solid lines in Figure 1). The values of fitting parameter K leading to the best fitting were $K = 28.6 \text{ kJ/m}^3$ for 21 nm CoFeNCs and $K = 10.6 \text{ kJ/m}^3$ for 14 nm IONCs. The slight discrepancies between experimental and theoretical results can be related to the hydrodynamic size distribution or dipolar interactions not considered in the model, or small differences of the K values. Note that K values in the simulations reasonably agree with those obtained from ACS. These parameters were kept constant in the numerical simulations for different viscosities.

Numerical simulations allow to also probe the sensitivity of magnetic dynamics to viscosity as a function of H_{MAX} . Figures 1C and 6 show the AC hysteresis loops for 14 nm IONCs dispersed in media with different viscosities and field intensities of 24 and 4 kA/m, respectively. Although AC hysteresis loops at 24 kA/m are slightly influenced by η values in the upper range (85.9 mPa·s); lower viscosities do not lead to significant variations in AC hysteresis loops. This behaviour opposes the observations at lower field intensity (4 kA/m) where a value of $\eta = 3.5 \text{ mPa}\cdot\text{s}$ is enough to appreciate significant variations of the shape and A of the AC hysteresis loops (i.e. H_C , M_R , M_{MAX}) with respect to $\eta = 0.9 \text{ mPa}\cdot\text{s}$ (see Figure 6). Such behaviour is ascribed to the capability of the external AC magnetic field (\vec{H}_{ex}) to generate magnetic torques (see ESI). Magnetic torques, already introduced in recent studies,^{9-10, 26, 31, 41-42} are manifested in two different ways: as an internal rotation of the magnetic moment \vec{m} of the MNPs and as a physical rotation of the MNPs in a liquid medium. Consequently, the dependence on H_{MAX} of such coexistent phenomena influences the Néel and Brownian rotational mechanisms, determining the τ_{Beff} and τ_{Neff} values, respectively (Figures 5C and G). The variation of the prevalent effective relaxation time (from τ_{Neff} to τ_{Beff}) with H_{MAX} (4 and 24 kA/m) partially explains why AC hysteresis loops of 14 nm IONCs are

so sensitive to η at 4kA/m. However, the key parameter required to explain such observations is the particle size distribution. Figures 5A-D show that l_c -which defines V and consequently the anisotropy energy barrier- leads to the raise of the τ_{Neff} values. Hence, the crossover between τ_{Neff} and τ_{Beff} regimes is favored by the size distribution (i.e. large values of Δl_c). Therefore, when the dynamical magnetic contribution of MNPs of a given l_c is weighted according to the related size histogram (Figures S1D-F), AC hysteresis loops are differently sensitive to viscosity depending on H_{MAX} (as shown in Figures 5B, D, F, H). Finally, the concomitant influence of H_{MAX} and size distribution on τ_{Neff} and τ_{Beff} is required to simulate the experimental results at low field intensities. The balance between several parameters determining τ_{Neff} and τ_{Beff} , namely size distribution, η , H_{MAX} and K eventually define the effective relaxation mechanism. Thus, AC hysteresis loops of 14 nm IONCs at $H_{\text{MAX}} = 24 \text{ kA/m}$ present no viscosity effects (Figure 1C) because the Néel relaxation is dominant for l_c values due to the stronger field-dependence of τ_{Neff} in comparison with τ_{Beff} ,¹¹ as opposed to the observations at 4 kA/m (Figures 5E-H). Moreover, the implicit consideration of both τ_{Neff} and τ_{Beff} in the stochastic LLG equation results in an overall good agreement between experimental and theoretical hysteresis loops under different experimental conditions. This model stresses the fact that not only MNP size and K favor Brownian relaxation process, but also low H_{MAX} and large size distribution. In a first approach, MNP size and K define the crossover between Néel and Brownian mechanisms, resulting in magnetic dynamics that are sensitive to viscosity for large MNP sizes and K values. Secondly, H_{MAX} and size distribution play also a critical role in the dynamic magnetic response, as both parameters strongly influence relaxation mechanisms. The so-produced results by feeding these parameters into the LLG equations provide a valuable guidance to predict the influence of viscosity on the magnetic heating efficiency under given MNP intrinsic (i.e. MNP size, size distribution, and K) and extrinsic conditions (H_{MAX}).

Conclusions

We have demonstrated the convenience of AC hysteresis loop measurements to determine the influence of viscosity on the dynamical magnetic response of MNPs through modelling experimental results. AC hysteresis loops from selected MNPs of different anisotropy constants dispersed in increasingly viscous media provide conclusive evidences on: i) the balance between those parameters determining the dominant magnetic relaxation process -namely size, size distribution, H_{MAX} and K - eventually define the viscosity sensitivity of the dynamical magnetic response of MNPs, ii) the viscosity dependence of the AC hysteresis area is correlated to that of the SAR, due to demagnetisation effects related to changes in the magnetisation dynamics when viscosity increases, and iii) size distributions and field-effective relaxation times in the stochastic LLG equation precisely reproduce the hysteresis loops in most of the considered cases. Our reported results encourage further exploration of the viscosity influence on the

magnetisation dynamics of MNPs, from dissipating the very slight discrepancies found between experiments and theory, to broadening the *KV* range explored by selecting suitable MNPs. Understanding which parameters determine the sensitivity of dynamical MNP magnetic response to viscosity is of great importance towards engineering MNPs with invariable magnetic heat losses.

Materials and methods

Magnetic nanoparticles

The MNPs studied in this work were iron oxide nanocubes with edge sizes of 14 ± 2 and 24 ± 4 nm and $\text{Co}_x\text{Fe}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ nanocubes with edge sizes of 21 ± 2 nm and cobalt fraction of $x = 0.7$, synthesised by thermal decomposition method as described elsewhere.^{33-34, 43} More details related to the MNP synthesis, surface modification and physico-chemical characterisation are described in ESI.

Magnetic characterisation

AC Magnetometry

Quasi-static conditions: field dependent magnetic measurements under quasi-static conditions were carried out at 260 K in an ever-cooled Magnetic Property Measurement System (*MPMS-XL*, Quantum Design) on MNP dispersion volumes of 100 μL at concentration of 2 $\text{g}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{L}$ (Figure S2). MNPs were physically blocked by slowly cooling the sample from room temperature to 260 K. The magnetisation signal was normalized to the mass of magnetic material (i.e. magnetite or cobalt ferrite).

Dynamical conditions: field dependent magnetic measurements under dynamical conditions (100 kHz and 24 kA/m) were performed using a home-made inductive magnetometer set up similar to the one described by Connord et al.⁴⁴ *AMF* was generated by an air-cooled Litz wire coil. Two contrariwise-wound compensated pick-up coils connected in series were set inside the AC magnetic field generator coil. The system quantifies the magnetic signal from MNP dispersions, and it is calibrated by comparing magnetisation values in a similar field intensity range obtained under AC and quasi-static magnetic field conditions. The AC magnetisation signal was normalized to the mass of magnetic material (i.e. magnetite or cobalt ferrite, respectively).

Calorimetry measurements

SAR values were determined for the studied MNPs dispersed in different glycerol dilutions by employing a non-adiabatic procedure described elsewhere.⁴⁵ The *AMF* employed is a home-made frequency and intensity adjustable field generator with frequencies up to 500 kHz and field intensities up to 56 kA/m. Temperature variations after *AMF* application were monitored via a commercial optical fibre probe TS2/2 connected to a FOTEMP2-16 two-channel signal conditioner from Optocon AG with an experimental error of ± 0.2 °C. The temperature vs time curves of IONC and CoFeNCs dispersions were recorded three times under similar dynamical conditions than AC hysteresis loops (100 kHz and 24 kA/m). Then, the

maximum slope values at initial times after switching on *AMF* (i.e. $dT/dt|_{\text{max}}$) were extracted. Average dT/dt slope value and standard deviation were determined for calculating SAR values by using the following expression:

$$\text{SAR} = \frac{C_d m_d}{m_{\text{mag}}} \left. \frac{dT}{dt} \right|_{\text{MAX}} \quad (3)$$

where C_d is the mass specific heat of the dispersion medium, m_d is the dispersion mass and m_{mag} is the mass of the magnetic material (i.e. magnetite or cobalt ferrite MNPs, respectively) and $dT/dt|_{\text{max}}$ is the average value of the maximum slope at initial times after switching on *AMF*. More details on C_d values of the employed glycerol dispersions are described in ESI.

Complex ac-susceptibility measurements

The complex AC-susceptibility (ACS) measurements were carried out using two setups⁴⁶ operating from 10 Hz to 10 kHz and 1 kHz to 1 MHz at magnetic field amplitudes of 0.46 kA/m and 0.07 kA/m, respectively. The ACS measurements at lower frequencies (2 Hz to 9 kHz) were performed using a fluxgate-based rotating magnetic field setup at 0.16 kA/m magnetic field amplitude.⁴⁷ The ACS measurements were carried out at 295 K in a volume of 150 μL of MNP dispersions with different glycerol fractions (0%, 36%, 81%, and 86%) but at fixed iron concentration of 2 $\text{g}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{L}$.

Numerical simulations

The curve-fitting of ACS measurements was performed using a least-squares fit routine to solve Debye equations and written in MATLAB. The routine uses the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm which is a powerful scheme for non-linear problems. Numerical simulations of AC hysteresis loops were based on calculating modified stochastic LLG equation describing the dynamics of the magnetic moments \vec{m} :

$$\frac{d\vec{m}}{dt} = \frac{\mu_0}{2\tau_0 KV} \left[\frac{m}{\lambda} \vec{m} \times (\vec{H}_{\text{eff}} + \vec{H}_{\text{th}}) - \vec{m} \times \vec{m} \times (\vec{H}_{\text{eff}} + \vec{H}_{\text{th}}) \right] \quad (4)$$

where τ_0 , which is given by $\tau_0 = m/2\gamma\lambda KV_c$, is the attempt frequency, m is the magnitude of the magnetic moment, γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, λ is a dimensionless damping coefficient, K is the magnetic anisotropy constant, and V is the individual MNP volume. The effective magnetic field \vec{H}_{eff} has been calculated assuming a uniaxial magnetic anisotropy and neglecting magnetic dipolar interactions; thus:

$$\vec{H}_{\text{eff}} = \vec{H}_{\text{ex}} + \vec{H}_{\text{K}} \quad (5)$$

where $\vec{H}_{\text{K}} = \frac{2KV}{\mu_0 m} \vec{m} \cdot \vec{n}$, and \vec{n} is unit vector along the easy axis.

Thermal fluctuations have been taken into account in the form of a random torque (as described in ESI). The influence of the applied field on the Néel and Brownian relaxation times as well as their relative contribution to their relaxation processes have been computed through the following set of equations:

$$\tau_{\text{Beff}} = \frac{\tau_{\text{B}}}{\sqrt{1+0.07\xi^2}} \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{\text{Neff}} = \tau_{\text{N}} \frac{\exp(\sigma h^2)}{(1-h^2)(\cosh \xi - h \sinh \xi)} \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma = \frac{KV}{k_B T}$, $\xi = \frac{\mu_0 M_s V H_{ac}}{k_B T}$, $h = \frac{\xi}{2\sigma}$, τ_N and τ_B are Néel and Brown relaxation times in the absence of an external field (Equations 1 and 2). For more realistic results, the experimental nanoparticle size distributions were inserted in the relevant equations. The algorithm was developed in C++ with CUDA running on a graphics processing unit (NVIDIA Tesla C2075). More details on *numerical simulations of the magnetic properties under AMF* are described in ESI.

Acknowledgements

This work has received funding from European Union's H2020 and FP7 (NOCANTHER, GA n° 685795; NANOMAG, GA n° 604448; Mag(net)icFun PITN-GA-2012-290248), European Research Council (Starting ERC grant ICARO, contract n°. 678109), Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MAT2013-47395-C4-3-R) and Comunidad de Madrid (NANOFRONTMAG-CM, S2013/MIT-2850), Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (S) funded by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science KAKENHI (15H05764). The European COST Action TD1402 (RADIOMAG) and Ramon y Cajal subprogram (RYC-2011-09617) are also acknowledged. Mr. Emilio Artés and the Advanced Instrumentation Unit (iMdea Nanociencia) are acknowledged for technical assistance.

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